

STAGES OF FORMATION OF VOLUNTARY QUALITIES IN FUTURE
MILITARY SERVANTS

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Voluntary adjectives in man real in the circumstances is formed i.e requirements perform in the process developed goes DAKasatkina he said, Irodvai adjectives from youth formed, it is adult requirements, as well as in society there is has been norms, law and decisions through improve goes.

K. G. Dedyukhin military of servants professional activity for important listed as “ Constructive to activity separately attention looking at him crimes detection, investigation to do, the risks prevention get, hidden criminals search according to, fast actions to planning directed mental activity that describes That is cognitive activity done increase in the process thinking basically, still unknown was to questions answer to find encourages or thinking power situation solution is enough.

V. M. Burkina this ability type analysis enough so, him military service employee in person formed information transmission and exchange get, organization instructions without words compliance do it knowing is complicated in the circumstances work organize do it get such as abilities type that calls From this except, future military servant for a must counted communicative able type too different, in our opinion him good without mastering it never one to success achieved it won't be.

A. A. to Maksimov apparently, military of the servant communicative activity is communication through necessary information take knowledge, practical fast tasks solution to do for , others with directly good mouth in communication will be get and others So, every one military servant communication in the process to others good effect do it get for, high mind and knowledge and skill, strong the will to the likes too have to be must is counted.

Researcher V. M. Smirnov own in their research military servants military - professional in preparation important counted, some features on stop, military servants for necessary was neuropsychic personal features to the following it says

- psychic of processes plasticity (flexibility);
- reactivity and optimal level of activity;
- high sensitivity (external to the effects neuropsychic of sensitivity increase);
- resistance shows get (started activity done to increase hindrance who does external and internal to the circumstances resistance);
- emotional stability;
- high emotional of intellect availability;
- worry level scarcity;
- tolerance and national affiliation

V. M. Statniy own in their research higher military education institutions cadets activity analysis enough since, first of all, theirs to the goal to achieve take coming optional of their actions the following features divides :

1. Voluntary actions are conscious, purposeful, own decision with done increase are actions;

2. Voluntary action done increase for, has always action perform for acceptance to be done basics ie objective and subjective conditions to be necessary;

3. Voluntary actions - the beginning decision or him done in raising manifestation to be high motivation to the power have

4. Voluntary action is known of mechanisms performance at the expense of manifestation being, then purpose, motivation, desire, need, decision, intellect, emotion, worldview and professional competence etc with addition gets stronger.

G. A. Nechiporenko meaning with in other words, the future military in servants important voluntary features of formation condition as, psychological features was, impulsivity and consideration, caution, remembering to stay and high level common to the intellect have to be such as attention get very important

Summary who does if it is voluntary adjectives given external from situations independent, individual mental dynamic formation process is counted, his main types to the goal orientation, initiative, determination, endurance, self catch knowledge, independence, organization, courage, efficiency such as adjectives is entered. Therefore, voluntary adjectives mental of actions basis, it is dynamic development to the stage has

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